

Dynamic Eclipse Broadcast (DEB) Initiative

Eclipse Checklist

1 April 2024

(DEB Information at debinitiative.org)

Fill in this table with the times for your exact observation location:

Expected Meridian Flip: _____
Start setup \geq 1 hour before 1 st Contact: _____
Start solar_photosphere_PSS_Upload.py 2 minutes before 1 st Contact: _____
1 st Contact: _____
Stop photosphere 10 minutes before 2 nd Contact: _____
<u>Check focus and alignment</u>
Start totality.py 1 minute before 2 nd Contact: _____
2 nd Contact: _____
3 rd Contact: _____
Stop totality.py after 3 rd contact
4 th Contact: _____

Day Before Eclipse

- Make sure the laptop has sufficient memory available (225 GB). Clean out old images and SER files.
- Fully charge all batteries: mount, laptop, back-up batteries, etc.
- Sleep, if you can.

Eclipse Day

Set-Up and Alignments

- Change Power & Battery settings on laptop - make sure the device never goes to sleep!
- Mount leveled and pointed north (correct for magnetic declination).
- Telescope completely set up, balanced, solar filter on.
- Connect iOptron mount to phone via WIFI, sync time/date and sync location.
- Take a screenshot of the location window in iOptron Commander on your phone.
- Turn off iOptron Commander on your phone and disconnect from the mount's WIFI.
- Find Sun, set good exposure and get the best focus possible.
- Correctly orient the camera and check rotation. Use the set screw to ensure the camera does not rotate during the eclipse.
- Fine tune drift alignment. Tighten the knobs down to make sure mount alignment does not shift if accidentally bumped during the eclipse.
- Set-up Complete before First Contact!**

Before and During the Eclipse

- Run the upload-shortcut from the desktop.
- At least 2 minutes before 1st Contact (Beginning of Eclipse):** begin running solar_photosphere_PSS_Upload.py script.
- If you have internet access, check debra.physics.siu.edu to make sure your images are uploading to the server.
- Enjoy! Regularly monitor the image in SharpCap to keep Sun centered in FOV if it drifts. Also check focus regularly as temperature may change focus.
- During the partial eclipse, take group photos, “action shots”, etc.
- 10 minutes before 2nd Contact:** STOP the stop solar_photosphere_PSS_Upload.py with STOP button in SharpCap.
- Recenter image and refocus image one last time.
- 1 minute before 2nd Contact:** run the Totality.py script, have someone block the telescope with a cardboard screen and remove the solar filter. DO NOT BUMP the telescope!
- After Diamond Ring (2nd Contact/Start of Totality):** Lower the cardboard to collect data. Enjoy the eclipse!! If something goes wrong now, it is too late to fix it.
- After 2nd Diamond Ring (3rd Contact/End of Totality):** Immediately cover the telescope again and put the solar filter back on.
- Immediately use the STOP button in SharpCap to stop the Totality.py script.
- Re-center the Sun on the image and then restart the solar_photosphere_PSS_Upload script.
- Regularly monitor the image in SharpCap to keep Sun centered in FOV if it drifts. Also check focus regularly and refocus as necessary.
- 2 minutes after 4th Contact (End of Eclipse):** STOP the stop solar_photosphere_PSS_Upload.py with STOP button in SharpCap.
- Take calibration data:** flats and darks!
- Back-up data in a second location (USB drive, etc).
- Congratulations!! Time to party like its1999!

After Everything Else

- Use rclone to upload totality, darks, flats folders to debra
- Make sure the exact GPS coordinates of your observing site are correctly loaded into spreadsheet.....
- Upload any “action shots” or brief videos you’d like to share into your team’s folder on the Google Drive.

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